

WEBSITE DEVELOPMENT FOR RAC PUNE PASHAN

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, there is a boom in website development as all the businesses, entities and organizations want an online presence. One of the crucial things about a website is User Interface and User Experience as normal users don't care about how the website is working in backend. The project is more focussed on the user experience that will leave an impact about the organization. To enhance user experience we have focussed on concepts like empathy mapping and user personas.

The project report has been prepared based on available data, forecasts provided by experts and other project management tools. The real life situation can be little different depending on the circumstances. The members working in the team will get a fixed amount at the end of the project. Any inclusion or deduction is possible as we have enough buffer time. Risks has been estimated based on common issues faced by this type of project. CPM method has been used to estimate time and creating Gantt chart. Spreadsheet (EXCEL) analysis has been used to do CPM. A detailed network diagram has been drawn to describe every step clearly. A register form is included in the appendix section to monitor the project through its life span. Risk register should be updated at every meeting. Full effort has been given to complete each and every pros and cons, so that they are taken into account

Keywords: React js, Express web-framework, Mental health, Node js, Face-rec chatbot

I. INTRODUCTION

This report traces the method and considerations involved in building web site for a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO). The reason of the site is to set up a solid online nearness, improve communication and engagement with partners, advance the organization's mission and targets, and encourage raising money endeavors. The report gives an outline of key steps included in site improvement, counting arranging, plan, substance creation, usefulness, and continuous upkeep.

A) Motivation

Rotaract club of pune pashan being a non-profit organization features a awesome affect on the society and to induce the results on the bigger scale we chosen

to require the sponsored project from Rotaract Club of Pune Pashan. The most thought process of this site will be to reach the foremost individuals to connect this community.

Rotaract Locale 3131 which has been the foremost impactful Area in Rotary-Rotaract organization and to work on this extend is itself a huge inspiration.

B) Objective

The objective of a Rotaract Club site is to serve as a central online center that successfully communicates the club's mission, exercises, and values whereas locks in individuals and the community. The site ought to point to realize the taking after goals:

II. MODERN TRENDS AND HONES IN SITE IMPROVEMENT

A) .Responsive Plan

Responsive plan is not an option but a need. With the expansion of versatile gadgets, it is basic for websites to adjust to different screen sizes and resolutions. Responsive plan guarantees that clients have a steady and ideal encounter in any case of the gadget they are utilizing. Present day css systems, such as Bootstrap and Establishment, make it easier than ever to make responsive websites..

B) Performance Optimization

Site speed and execution are basic for client fulfillment and look engine rankings. Designers ought to center on optimizing page stack times by compressing images, minifying CSS and JavaScript, and leveraging browser caching. Content delivery systems (CDNs) can too be utilized to disperse site resources proficiently. Innovations like WebP pictures and lazy loading can encourage progress execution..

Site security may be a beat concern, given the expanding number of cyber dangers. Designers must execute best hones for security, counting utilizing HTTPS, remaining up to date with security patches, and sanitizing client inputs to avoid SQL infusion and cross-site scripting (XSS) assaults. Standard security reviews and entrance testing are significant to recognize vulnerabilities.

Client involvement (UX) is vital in site improvement. Websites should be outlined with a center on user-friendly navigation, instinctive formats, and openness. Joining feedback mechanisms, like client studies and analytics, can help designers persistently move forward the client involvement. A/B testing and convenience testing can moreover give important bits of knowledge into client inclinations.

Substance Administration Frameworks, such as WordPress, Joomla, and Drupal, are well known choices for site advancement. They give a user-friendly interface for substance overhauls and offer a wide range of plugins and topics to amplify usefulness and plan. Developers must select the proper CMS for their venture and keep it overhauled to ensure security.

III. LITERATURE WORK

A study in 30th june 2021 in Online Monitoring and Visualization with ROS and ReactJS with Its

architecture let the application to be deployed on a remote hosting and, moreover, it's modular structure allows to be embedded into other developing ReactJS application

In 16th May 2021 A study of Smart Attendance Marking System using face recognition is done and it shows Facial features are extracted from using cnn's (convolutional neural networks) using MongoDB Database management, software requirements- Open CV , Tkinter , VisualStudio. principle component analysis (PCA) used for image processing

Yufeng Chen in 2021 study about NodeSRT: A Selective Regression Testing Tool for Node.js Application which Using a change-based selection technique, obtaining a function call relationship with dynamic analysis, collecting file dependency with static analysis, NodeSRT reduces regression tests in short running time and high inclusiveness and precision.

Mohanish Bawane Ishaligawande &Vaishnavi Joshi on 1st January 2022 take Review on technologies used in Mernstack in which The MERN stack (MongoDB , Express , React , Node.js) is a popular technology stack for building web applications .MongoDB :- MongoDB is a NoSQL database that stores data in a flexible, schema-less format using JSON- like documents.

Express is a minimal and flexible Node.js web application framework tha React:React is a JavaScript library for building user interfaces, particularly single-page applications (SPAs t simplifies building robust APIs and web applications Node.js: Node.js is a runtime environment for executing JavaScript on the server side

IV. SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE REQUIREMENT

html, css, Javascript Technology Stack: MongoDB, ExpressJs, ReactJs, NodeJ Database Language: Mongoddb Backend Development (Node.js and Express):Create an Express application for your server.Define the database schema and models using MongoDB/Mongoose.Implement APIs for user authentication, course information, news, events, and other relevant data.Frontend Development (React):Set up a React application for the frontend.Design and develop the user interface components for various sections of the website, including the homepage, course pages, event listings, and more.Implement user authentication and authorization on the client sid

V. LIMITATION

While Rotaract Club websites offer various benefits, they also come with limitations that need to be considered.

Not all community members may have access to the internet or be tech-savvy, limiting the reach of the website to a certain demographic.

Websites require ongoing maintenance, updates, and content management. Ensuring the website remains up-to-date can be time-consuming.

Technical glitches, downtime, or compatibility problems with various devices and browsers can affect the user experience.

In regions or communities with limited internet access or digital literacy

VI. SOCIAL IMPLICATION

The social implications of a Rotaract Club website can be far-reaching and have a positive impact on both the club's members and the broader community. Here are some of the social implications of a Rotaract Club website:

The website facilitates networking among Rotaract Club members. It enables members to connect with like-minded individuals, share experiences, and collaborate on projects, thereby fostering a sense of community and social cohesion.

Rotaract clubs provide young people with opportunities for personal and professional development, leadership training, and networking. Through involvement in club activities, members gain valuable skills, confidence, and a sense of purpose, empowering them to become active agents of change in their communities and beyond.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE AND STUDY

We would add a mobile application in sync with the website.

It can be used to automatically tag users in photos and videos. It can also aid in content recommendation algorithms, helping users discover content and connections that are more relevant to them.

VIII. FIGURES AND TABLES

TABLE 1
Website collection description

Collection	Description
Admin	Collection contains details of Administrative, admin has complete access level for website and login credentials will be provided.
Past core team	This collection Contain Past core Details
Board of Directors	This collection Contain Board of Directors
Avenue	In this collection different Avenue are present
Club Project	Collection Contains club past and upcoming project
Blog	This collection has the information about projects in forms of blogs

TABLE 2
List of Modules

Module 1	Data Flow Diagram
Module 2	Entity Relationship daigram
Module 3	UML Diagram
Module 4	Sequence Diagram
Module 5	Activity Diagram

C) DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

The Rotaract Club website is represented as a single process, interacting with external entities. This diagram provides an overview of the data flows into and out of the website

1) DFD LEVEL O

2) DFD LEVEL 1

E) ENTITY REALTIONSHIP DIAGRAM

This entity represents the members, administrators, and other users of the website. It typically includes attributes like User ID, Name, Email, and Role

3) DFD LEVEL 2

D) UML DIAGRAM

Use case diagrams illustrate the interactions between users and the website in terms of use cases or functionalities. Actors include members, administrators, and guests

F) SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

A sequence diagram for a Rotaract Club website can illustrate the interactions and communication between various components or objects within the system.

Figure 1: Home Page of Rotarct website

Figure 2: Team Leaders of Club

Figure 3: Expression Detection Page

Figure 4: Rotarct events Page

G) ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

An activity diagram for a Rotarct Club website can illustrate the flow of activities or processes within the website.

IX. RESULTS

X. COPYRIGHT AND LICENSES

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XI. CONCLUSION

Developed website for Rotaract Club of Pune Pashan using MERN stack with major focus on enhancing the user experience

The Rotaract Club website, as a crucial point of interaction, needs to evolve to better serve its members and community. A comprehensive redesign plan that includes responsive design, a content management system, improved navigation, interactive features, and accessibility enhancements can elevate the website's impact. By embracing these changes, the Rotaract Club can foster greater engagement, community involvement, and a more enriched member experience.

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